

reconFIGURE: Confronting Audiences with Digital Doppelgängers

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Fig. 1. Doppelgängers in a self-organized mass.

This paper describes the artistic context, technical implementation, user study, evaluation and future work around reconFIGURE, a participatory installation exploring the transformation of human bodies through computational systems. The installation involves capturing visitors' images, transforming these into animated 3D *doppelgängers*, and projecting them on a large-screen. Unique in its rapid transformation from 2D to 3D, reconFIGURE highlights the aesthetic-social repercussions of transforming whole human body images using machine learning.

CCS Concepts: • **Applied computing** → **Media arts**; • **Computing methodologies** → **Animation**.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: computation, algorithmic, generative, human interaction, interface, installation, interaction, machine learning, perception, interaction, body

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1 INTRODUCTION

ReconFIGURE is a participatory installation exploring how bodies are re-imagined by computing machines and the humour and confusion experienced when these machines create imperfect representations. The installation consists of a (1) capturing station where the visitors' frontal 2D image is rapidly transformed into an animated 3D reconstruction; and (2) a projected image that combines the captured figures together. Encountering their re-animated selves, visitors thus bear witness to the mutations generated by the machine processes. To create this experience, reconFIGURE optimizes technologies from 3D human reconstruction, machine learning, and computer graphics. Incorporating full body capture into a participatory work, however, remains challenging as the process of reconstruction still requires significant time and labour. This article thus describes the methods necessary in order to reach potential novel forms of artistic expression with such systems.

2 CONTEXT

ReconFIGURE probes how computational systems capture, represent and transform human bodies [Hansen 2012; Hayles 2000]. In art criticism, this theme has long been examined through notions of “technical exteriorisation” [Wegenstein 2010]; “data bodies” [Salazar 2023]; and the “undigital image” where a disconnect is felt between subject and body through computational image making [Zylinska 2020]. This distinguishes reconFIGURE from art works where real time video images of the self enable interactivity between participant and environment [Kruger 1974; Rokeby 1986; Utterback 1999] and from generative AI projects that focus mainly on manipulating the human face using database images [Klingeman 2020; Obvious 2018]. While artists have employed LiDAR or motion capture for body reconstruction of avatars [Pietroszek et al. 2022; Zeidler and McGinity 2023] or in dance [Downie and Kaiser 2019], these projects neither focus on 2D to 3D image transformation nor on the art theoretical context of digital body representation in which we situate our work.

This tension between body and captured other also marks reconFIGURE as an encounter with digital “doppelgängers.” Coined by the 18th century German writer Jean Paul, the doppelgänger is a ghostly counterpart for a living person, seen as an omen or sign of death. Freud later argues that encountering one's double produces an experience of “doubling, dividing and interchanging the self” [Freud 2017, p. 321] while recently, critic Naomi Klein uses the doppelgänger as a commentary on our culture's tendency to create digital likenesses that we confuse with real people [Klein 2023]. reconFIGURE's doppelgängers, however, are not perfect but riddled with errors and biases (see 6 below), suggesting the fallibility of machines to capture the richness and diversity of human corporeality.

3 ARTISTIC EXPERIENCE

Aesthetically, reconFIGURE evokes the uncanny - an unsettling feeling that feels oddly familiar [Freud 2017] - when confronting a digital other. To achieve this, we structure the experience in two parts: (1) capture and transformation of the visitors' body image and (2) the reanimation of the image in an audio-visual environment that suggests bodies suspended in outer space or a liminal zone between life and death.

To begin the experience, visitors stand before a station with a camera and a monitor in portrait format and initiate a specific pose to initiate the reconstruction process (see section 4 and Figure

Fig. 2. Dramaturgical structure of reconFIGURE.

3). Once reconstructed, the double appears on the monitor, moving independently of the visitors' movement. This confrontation with one's doppelgänger has an intimate quality, yet the doppelgänger quickly disappears from the display, reappearing in a larger projection in the room. The individual self thus joins other doppelgängers, inviting the visitor to search out their copy among the others.

In the projected image, the doppelgänger collective moves through a set of sequences in a 13-minute cycle. The grouping of these copies creates a sense of collective identity and connectedness. To symbolize their autonomy and recent re-creation, the 3D figures are visually displayed with an oily iridescent substance that fades over the cycle. The dramatic structure is in three parts: "Emergence," "Suspension," "Rebirth" (see Figure 2). In "Emergence", the doppelgängers walk slowly in linear group formations. Gradually, the formations break down as the figures separate, lose gravity and ascend upwards. The doppelgängers begin to turn in a twisting ring forming a self-organized mass before being violently repelled from each other and left to drift lifelessly in the empty space ("Suspension"). Finally, in "Rebirth" the figures regain momentum, floating like fish and interacting in complex ways as they become visually distorted and lose their resemblance to the captured image. In the cycle's conclusion, they reunite in smaller groups, regaining their initial appearance before again losing gravity. Plummeting from the screen, the conclusions create a sense of both unease and release before the cycle begins anew.

Enabled by real-time dynamics generation in the Unity 3D engine, the visual transformation of the projected doubles suggests the gradual disappearance of individuality and human essence. Floating in a murky space, the doppelgängers' behaviour is controlled by global and local systems, lending dynamics to the overall narrative and inviting viewers to confront the tension between individual agency and external influence from the environment on their actions. Consisting of ambient soundscape and structured score, the audio design also expresses these tensions. The soundscape comprises elements generated by noise algorithms that run through the same processing in parallel and accentuate the physical movements of the doppelgängers and the forces that act within the space. Additional tonal layers articulate materiality and texture of the bodies. This parallelism generates a rich sonic structure that reveals physical and textural characteristics. In contrast, the score introduces harmonic elements to emphasize crucial dramatic moments in the cycle. Initially

Fig. 3. Installation system architecture.

playing in a particular key, the harmonic structure disintegrates as the cycle unfolds, with decreasing glissandi underscoring the increasing suspense.

4 TECHNICAL IMPLEMENTATION

ReconFIGURE combines technologies from 3D human reconstruction, machine learning and computer graphics to enable the experience described above 3. The architecture has been designed to be modular in order to enable seamless integration of diverse technologies and facilitate development and customisation. As shown in Figure 3, each component in the architecture is loosely coupled to others using standard protocols (HTTP and OSC), while ensuring rapid adaptability to specific exhibition sites. A notable aspect is the architecture’s division into the two primary areas of capturing and display.

4.1 Reconstruction System

To overcome the challenges of capture, and reconstruction, we introduce the end-to-end reconstruction pipeline *Nevo* (Neural Volumetric Capture). *Nevo* combines machine learning models and traditional algorithms to automatically convert a single 2D human image into a volumetric digital representation and enables rapid reconstruction of digital humans without the need for expertise in 3D modeling or software development. While 3D human reconstruction has been heavily researched in computer graphics, systems have focused mainly on 3D mesh reconstruction [Zheng et al. 2019], and extracting attributes (e.g., height or weight) from a 2D image [Choutas et al. 2022]. As well, most of these solutions are not intended to be used as complete systems, but to fulfil a certain core task (e.g., reconstruction). To integrate such systems into an artistic experience, additional steps are thus required before and after conversion to a 3D model, including a simple data format in order to provide the mesh or volumetric sequences to game engines and other systems. Such process can thus enable complex machine learning- assisted human digital reconstruction in hours [Desaulles et al. 2022] or even minutes. Although existing end-to-end systems [Li et al. 2019, 2021] provide not only reconstruction but also an environment to further integrate the generated human representation into a real-world application, most implementations of these systems are not publicly available for use. *Nevo* improves this by providing an extensible pipeline framework that is available as open source.

In professional art exhibitions with limited setup time, the system must also be easy to calibrate outside of a controlled laboratory environment. Thus, *Nevo*’s main focus is to provide a simple and

Fig. 4. Nevo reconstruction pipeline.

stable system that can be used as a reliable component. Nevo implements the function of generating a 3D human pose from a monocular image using PIFuHD [Saito et al. 2020], which offers high image resolution and full-body image processing. Compared to other implementations, PIFuHD’s source code and pre-trained weights are publicly available. In addition, the reconstruction in PIFuHD is not based on a parametric human body model such as SMPL [Loper et al. 2015], but works directly on the mesh data, resulting in more detail. The pre-trained dataset used for PIFuHD was evaluated and discussed in section 6.

Nevo’s technical framework is a pipeline (see figure 4) consisting of several nodes, each performing a specific task. The pipeline input is a single image or video, which is then processed and output as a mesh or mesh sequence. By including less compute-heavy pre- and post-processing nodes like [Bazarevsky et al. 2020] for pose estimation, improving the mesh writing process with the Open3D library [Zhou et al. 2018] and accelerating the grid evaluation process using Numba [Lam et al. 2015], the end-to-end inference time for a single frame with PIFuHD could be reduced from ≈ 4 to ≈ 1.3 seconds on a standard NVIDIA 2080 Ti. As PIFuHD does not output a texture, it was necessary to implement a method to texture the mesh by extracting the person’s front texture from the input image and orthographically projecting it onto the mesh. To infer the back texture, a generative adversarial network (GAN) [Goodfellow et al. 2014] based on the contrastive unpaired translation model [Park et al. 2020] was trained with about 3000 renderings of digital human models (Figure 5). Furthermore, Nevo generates an animated rig and calculates the weight painting without any manual steps. The rigging process is based on the 2D body part segmentation bodypix [Garg 2020] and a heuristic-based algorithm we call *Instance Rig*.

5 USER STUDIES

In 2023, reconFIGURE was shown in three professional exhibitions, each with different screen configurations (from single to multi-screen projection), and lighting conditions, which required continual adaptation. Working outside the laboratory “in the wild” with shifting publics also posed challenges to user experience data acquisition using traditional laboratory methods. We therefore used a mixed *quant-qual* approach to collect and analyse user data including: 1) 5-point Likert scale survey (n=18, see results in Figure 6) (accessible via QR code) to collect quantitative feedback; 2) conducting informal interviews with visitors; and 3) ongoing observation by the artistic team.

The Likert scale allowed quantification of visitors’ experience of the installation. Informal interviews (n=30) provided further insights into visitors’ subjective experiences and emotional responses in order to understand the nuanced impact of the artistic elements. From the evaluations, some visitors described certain moments of the experience as unsettling, particularly in sequences involving loss of gravity and bodily control. Moreover, observations revealed different patterns of visitor engagement, with many visitors spending extended time in the installation over multiple cycles. In contrast, others showed reluctance and discomfort, particularly during the capture process. Based

Fig. 5. Reconstruction with input image (a), resulting in a mesh with: normal texture (b), RGB texture (c) and inferred RGB back-texture (d).

on these assessments, we made adjustments to reconFIGURE in different exhibitions, including accelerating the capture process and repositioning the capturing station to balance visibility with unobtrusiveness in the overall experience.

Fig. 6. Likert questionnaire evaluation (n=18)

6 DISCUSSION

ReconFIGURE balances humour with uncanniness by confronting the visitor with a transformed self-image (Figure 1). However, the installation’s reconstructions are not without problems. First, machine learning in artistic work generates ethical questions involving data set bias [Coeckelbergh 2020] and privacy issues around the capture of visitors’ images. We reflexively discuss how we address bias below while we dealt with user privacy through an informed consent statement electronically displayed on the capture station monitor, announcing that image data would not be further analyzed and would be destroyed in 24 hours. Second, glitches and errors occur due to recording difficulties and camera limitations. While these errors highlight current technological limits, they also point to areas for improvement through higher-sensitivity cameras, better neural networks and more accurate lighting control. Third, the system exhibits biases inherent in the datasets, notably in gender bias, where female visitors observed the assignment of high heels to their doppelgängers regardless of actual footwear. Analysis revealed that the dataset used to train the PIFuHD model features a disproportionate representation of women wearing high heels (>35%), despite almost equal gender distribution. Such biases become apparent when the network identified “feminine” characteristics, such as longer hair or female body shapes. Distinguishing

Fig. 7. Analysis of dataset used to train PIFuHD.

error from bias is challenging, hence the focus on specific imbalances in the dataset, such as the feature of high heels. An important observation is also the ableist bias in the dataset as all represented individuals appear as able-bodied, possessing four full limbs and standing. This lack of diversity suggests the critical need for more inclusive data representation in future iterations of such systems. The user studies show that reconFIGURE and its modules can be used as an important component in a professional exhibition context. The system is efficient to set up, maintenance-free and extendable for specific artist's wishes and ideas. Additionally, the potential of the Nevo pipeline for live performances, interactive installations, games, and virtual conferencing is significant as it opens up new possibilities for creative expression and audience engagement around issues of digital body transformation.

7 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

As reconFIGURE continues to be professionally exhibited internationally, ongoing enhancements are planned. A significant area is improving Nevo by integrating a more advanced reconstruction system [Xiu et al. 2023] which offers texture inference methods applied directly onto the mesh surface, rather than relying on 2D projections. Another technical advancement is implementing a machine learning-based rigging algorithm [Kim et al. 2021]. Addressing biases by diversifying the dataset is another critical aspect of future work. This includes a more inclusive range of models that break from binary gender appearances, include physical disabilities, (e.g., individuals in wheelchairs or having visible impairments, such as missing limbs) as well as figures with non-standard physical proportions all of which can work against the "normative discursive frameworks" of body types [Niehaus and Fiebrink 2021]. Finally, we are exploring the potential of integrating XR technologies (e.g., video passthrough) to transition the visitor away from being an external observer focused

on a frontal projection to being amidst an environment where the digital doppelgängers seem to occupy physical space. This shift is expected to enhance not only the level of engagement but also increase the degree of co-presence between fellow visitors and their doppelgängers. Such a move might thus proffer an even more uncanny experience with these technologies in the future.

REFERENCES

- Valentin Bazarevsky, Ivan Grishchenko, Karthik Raveendran, Tyler Zhu, Fan Zhang, and Matthias Grundmann. 2020. BlazePose: On-device Real-time Body Pose tracking. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2006.10204>
- Vasileios Choutas, Lea Müller, Chun-Hao P. Huang, Siyu Tang, Dimitrios Tzionas, and Michael J. Black. 2022. Accurate 3D Body Shape Regression using Metric and Semantic Attributes. In *Proceedings IEEE Conf. on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*.
- Mark Coeckelbergh. 2020. *AI ethics*. MIT Press.
- Chloé Desaulles, Alexandre Devaux, Or Fleisher, and Mark McKeague. 2022. Modeling key world cup moments with machine learning. <https://rd.nytimes.com/projects/modeling-key-world-cup-moments-with-machine-learning>
- Marc Downie and Paul Kaiser. 2019. Counterpart. <http://openendedgroup.com/artworks/counterpart.html>
- Sigmund Freud. 2017. The uncanny. In *Romantic Writings*. Routledge, 318–325.
- Anish Garg. 2020. Real-Time Person Segmentation – Based on Body Pix. *International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology* 6 (12 2020), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.46501/IJMTST061201>
- Ian Goodfellow, Jean Pouget-Abadie, Mehdi Mirza, Bing Xu, David Warde-Farley, Sherjil Ozair, Aaron Courville, and Yoshua Bengio. 2014. Generative Adversarial Nets. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, Z. Ghahramani, M. Welling, C. Cortes, N. Lawrence, and K.Q. Weinberger (Eds.), Vol. 27. Curran Associates, Inc. https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper_files/paper/2014/file/5ca3e9b122f61f8f06494c97b1afccf3-Paper.pdf
- Mark BN Hansen. 2012. *Bodies in code: Interfaces with digital media*. Routledge.
- N Katherine Hayles. 2000. How we became posthuman: Virtual bodies in cybernetics, literature, and informatics.
- Jeonghwan Kim, Hyeontae Son, Jinseok Bae, and Young Min Kim. 2021. Auto-rigging 3D Bipedal Characters in Arbitrary Poses. In *Eurographics 2021 - Short Papers*, Holger Theisel and Michael Wimmer (Eds.). The Eurographics Association. <https://doi.org/10.2312/egs.20211023>
- Naomi Klein. 2023. *Doppelgänger: A Trip into the Mirror World*. Knopf Canada.
- Mario Klingeman. 2020. Circuit Training. <https://underdestruction.com/2020/08/29/circuit-training/>
- Myron Kruger. 1974. Videoplace. <https://aboutmyronkrueger.weebly.com/videoplace.html>
- Siu Kwan Lam, Antoine Pitrou, and Stanley Seibert. 2015. Numba: A LLVM-Based Python JIT Compiler. In *Proceedings of the Second Workshop on the LLVM Compiler Infrastructure in HPC (Austin, Texas) (LLVM '15)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 7, 6 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2833157.2833162>
- Zhong Li, Lele Chen, Celong Liu, Yu Gao, Yuanzhou Ha, Chenliang Xu, Shuxue Quan, and Yi Xu. 2019. 3D Human Avatar Digitization from a Single Image. In *Proceedings of the 17th International Conference on Virtual-Reality Continuum and Its Applications in Industry (Brisbane, QLD, Australia) (VRCAI '19)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Article 12, 8 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3359997.3365707>
- Zhong Li, Lele Chen, Celong Liu, Fuyao Zhang, Zekun Li, Yu Gao, Yuanzhou Ha, Chenliang Xu, Shuxue Quan, and Yi Xu. 2021. Animated 3D human avatars from a single image with GAN-based texture inference. *Computers & Graphics* 95 (2021), 81–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cag.2021.01.002>
- Matthew Loper, Naureen Mahmood, Javier Romero, Gerard Pons-Moll, and Michael J. Black. 2015. SMPL: A Skinned Multi-Person Linear Model. *ACM Trans. Graph.* 34, 6, Article 248 (nov 2015), 16 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2816795.2818013>
- Kiona Hagen Niehaus and Rebecca Fiebrink. 2021. Making Up 3D Bodies: Artistic and Serendipitous Modeling of Digital Human Figures. *Proc. ACM Comput. Graph. Interact. Tech.* 4, 2, Article 23 (aug 2021), 9 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3468779>
- Obvious. 2018. Edmond de Belamy. <https://obvious-art.com/portfolio/edmond-de-belamy/>
- Taesung Park, Alexei A. Efros, Richard Zhang, and Jun-Yan Zhu. 2020. Contrastive Learning for Unpaired Image-to-Image Translation. In *European Conference on Computer Vision*.
- Krzysztof Pietroszek, Manuel Rebol, and Becky Lake. 2022. Dill Pickle: Interactive Theatre Play in Virtual Reality. In *Proceedings of the 28th ACM Symposium on Virtual Reality Software and Technology*. 1–2.
- David Rokeby. 1986. Very Nervous System. <http://www.davidrokeby.com/vns.html>
- Shunsuke Saito, Tomas Simon, Jason Saragih, and Hanbyul Joo. 2020. Pifuhd: Multi-level pixel-aligned implicit function for high-resolution 3d human digitization. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 84–93.
- Constanza Salazar. 2023. Challenging the “Data Body” in New Media Art, 1990s–Present. *Afterimage* 50, 2 (2023), 93–111.
- Camille Utterback. 1999. Text Rain. <https://camilleutterback.com/projects/text-rain/>

- Bernadette Wegenstein. 2010. Body. *Critical terms for media studies* (2010), 19–34.
- Yuliang Xiu, Jinlong Yang, Xu Cao, Dimitrios Tzionas, and Michael J. Black. 2023. ECON: Explicit Clothed humans Optimized via Normal integration. In *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*.
- Daniel Zeidler and Matthew McGinity. 2023. Bodylab: in virtuo sculpting, painting and performing of full-body avatars. *Proceedings of the ACM on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques* 6, 2 (2023), 1–12.
- Zerong Zheng, Tao Yu, Yixuan Wei, Qionghai Dai, and Yebin Liu. 2019. DeepHuman: 3D Human Reconstruction from a Single Image. In *The IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*.
- Qian-Yi Zhou, Jaesik Park, and Vladlen Koltun. 2018. Open3D: A Modern Library for 3D Data Processing. *CoRR* abs/1801.09847 (2018). arXiv:1801.09847 <http://arxiv.org/abs/1801.09847>
- Joanna Zylińska. 2020. *AI art: machine visions and warped dreams*. Open Humanities Press.